

Advanced Metering Infrastructure-Enabled Minimization of Power System Losses in Lebanon

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Abstract

Non-technical power losses (NTL) represent a significant proportion of electricity losses in developing as well as developed countries. More specifically, NTL in distribution sectors constitute the major part of the overall power losses at global level, and particularly in developing countries. They represent an avoidable financial loss for the utility thus imposing a substantial financial burden on governments as well as private utilities. The main objective of this paper is to determine, accurately, and to reduce, drastically, the NTL in the Lebanese power distribution sector by implementing a Power Line Carrier (PLC) based Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) system. The mechanism utilized to reduce system losses is based on correlating energy at various voltage levels, i.e., generation, transmission, distribution, and end users. In addition, this system has a significant impact on the loss reduction because it enables the local electric power utility to detect all types of

electricity theft. The proposed PLC based AMI system is compared to other communication media taking into consideration several factors such as optimum solution to minimize NTL, costs of implementation, and others.

Indexed keywords: AMI, TL, NTL, PLC, energy correlation, distribution system losses

Article History: Received: 03 October 2019 | Accepted: 27 December 2019 | Published: 13 January 2020

BACKGROUND

In providing electricity supply to end users, power losses constitute the amounts of electricity injected into the transmission and distribution grids but are not paid for by users. Total power losses have two components: technical and non-technical. Technical losses (TL) occur naturally and consist mainly of power dissipation due to Ohmic losses in electricity system components such as transmission and distribution lines, transformers, and measuring systems. NTL are caused by actions external to the power system and consist primarily of electricity theft, nonpayment by customers, and errors in accounting and record-keeping. These categories of losses are sometimes referred to as commercial, non-payment, and administrative losses.

NTL are related to the customer management process and include means of consciously defrauding the utility concerned. Theft of power can happen as a result of meter tampering or by bypassing the meter. Losses due to

metering inaccuracies are defined as the difference between the amount of energy actually delivered through the meters and the amount registered by the meters. In general, the most probable causes of NTL are:

- Tampering with meters to ensure lower recorded consumption reading,
- Errors in TL computation,
- Tapping (hooking) on LT lines,
- Arranging false readings by bribing meter readers,
- Bypassing the meter or otherwise making illegal connections,
- Ignoring unpaid bills,
- Faulty energy meters or un-metered supply,
- Errors and delay in meter reading and billing,
- Non-payment by customers.

Distribution network operators calculate NTL for different purposes, such as planning; reducing the network losses, assessing the network efficiency and operational decisions, and determining the optimum configuration of the network (Dashtaki e Haghifam, 2013).[12] Ideally losses in the distribution system should be around 3-5%. However, in developing countries distribution loss is around 20%, and therefore, there is an increasing trend in remedy the NTL problem (Khazae e Ghasempour, 2013). [25] NTL practices represent a prejudice with respect to the rest of consumers, since the energy losses influence the computation of reference tariffs, which in reality implies that nonfraudulent customers are covering for the loss caused by fraudulent customers (Coma-Puig e

Carmona, 2019).[10] In the industrial sector, NTL practices represent an unfair competition since companies avoiding paying their bills one way or another can reduce their production and operational costs, whereas companies that legally and fully pay their energy consumption bills will be at disadvantage. The annual world-wide costs for utilities due to NTL are estimated to be around USD 100 billion (Glauner *et al.*, 2018).[21] In the United States, NTL were estimated between 0.5% and 3.5% of gross annual revenue. These figures appear relatively low when compared to the losses faced by utilities in developing countries such as Bangladesh, India and Pakistan. Nevertheless, the loss amounted to between USD 1 billion and USD 10 billion. (Newbery, 2005).[33]

Studies have shown that a significant percentage of those amounts (in some cases more than 50 percent) becomes reduced demand when those users have to pay, because they adjust their consumption to their ability to pay for electricity services. NTL are estimated to account for up to 30% revenue losses to utilities (Alzoubi, 2005).[5]

System losses, in general, increase the operating costs of electric utilities and typically result in higher cost of electricity, and hence reduction of system losses enhance the economic, financial and social repercussions for the electric utility as well as the customers. Social and economic factors like literacy, income, and capacity building do also affect the losses rates in

rural dominated countries (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2018).[1]

Although some electrical power loss is inevitable, measures can still be implemented to ensure substantial reduction. As these losses are concentrated in the low-voltage network, their origins are spread along the whole system and are most critical at lower levels in the residential and small commercial sectors. Measures applied to this end are based on technology and on human initiatives and ingenuity. Overcoming and recovering NTL is essential and requires significant investment in the means of doing so.

Techniques Adopted for Detecting/Measuring of NTL

Nizar *et al.*, 2006,[34] presented a comprehensive review on NTL, load profiles and data mining techniques that are currently being used to minimize the NTL activities. It also presented on the contributing factors in load profiles of electricity customers, using the knowledge discovery in databases procedure, to determine the load profiles for different types of customers.

Nizar *et al.*, 2008,[34] presented a new approach to NTL analysis for utilities using the modern Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) computational technique. Carlos A. Dortolina and Ramón Nadira, 2005[16] proposed a top-down/bottom-up approach for accurately estimating TL in power distribution systems when a complete

set of modeling data is not available. The results yielded by these topdown and bottom-up approaches must be in agreement with each other. Otherwise, additional analysis needs to be conducted in order to reconcile the differences.

Cabral *et al.*,[7] 2004, described an application of rough sets in the fraud detection of electrical energy consumers. Rough sets concept was used to reduce the number of conditional attributes and the Minimal Decision Algorithm (MDA). The reduced information system derives a set of rules that reaches consumers behavior allowing the classification rule system to predict many fraud consumers' profiles.

Most of the previous researches on NTL depend fully on user behavior monitoring, analysis, and feature extraction. A type of standard methodology used by electricity companies to detect NTL is based on the study of customers who have null consumption during a certain period. This type of customer whose consumption is null can be identified as a source of NTL. The problem with this methodology is that this client does not always have an NTL because it can be, i.e. an unidentified unoccupied property (Guerrero *et al.*, 2018).[22]

The use of neural networks is common in several cases of fraudulent user detection due to the flexibility and capability to associate the features of users with fraudulent patterns (Zheng

et al., 2018). [42] However, one of the disadvantages of working with an artificial neural network is the need for real life samples other than the training set to evaluate the network performance.

Coma-Puig and Carmona,[10] 2019 explored the possibilities that exist in the implementation of Machine-Learning techniques for the detection of NTL in customers. They reported how the success in detecting NTL can help to better control the energy provided to customers, avoiding a misuse and hence improving the sustainability of the service that power utilities provide.

Glauner *et al.*, 2018[21] provided suggestions on how to further reduce NTL by not only carrying out inspections, but also by implementing market reforms, increasing administrative efficiency of utilities and improving communication between utilities, authorities and customers.

Uparela *et al.*, 2018 [39] developed a novel methodology to identify residential fraudulent users by using intelligent systems that system consist of three fundamental modules. The first module performs the classification of users with similar power consumption curves using self-organizing maps and genetic algorithms. The second module allows carrying out the monthly electricity demand forecasting through of recursive adjustment of ARIMA models. The third module performs the detection of fraudulent users through an artificial neural network for pattern recognition.

The implementation of advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) has benefits in detecting fraudulent users who have billing such as flexibility and adaptability in any electrical system, monitoring data in real time with reduction of electricity costs due to more precise consumption and more accurate location of NTL. This is achieved through the use of intelligent electronics devices, measures taken through an automated process and advanced measurement systems (Leite e Mantovani, 2016; Su, 2016).[26] The main feature of this technology is the increase of efficiency of estimation algorithms and classification of users, such as distribution state estimation (DSE), A-Star algorithm and semi-definite relaxation (SDR).

Buzau *et al.*,[6] 2018 proposed a methodology which uses the Smart Meter (SM) data and auxiliary databases to formulate various characteristics of the customer's consumption behavior and also to provide additional information with regard to the geographical and technological characteristics of the SM. These characteristics are afterwards introduced into several supervised machine learning algorithms for model selection and evaluation. The models have been trained, validated and tested using real data from all the customers of the largest electricity utility in Spain, with a contracted power higher than 50 kW.

While TL can be calculated using load flow method of power system, NTL are

more difficult to measure. As NTL cannot be computed and measured easily, but it can be estimated from preliminary results, i.e. the result of TL is first computed and subtracted from the total losses to obtain the balance as NTL. The TL are computed using appropriate load-flow studies simulated under Matlab environment

In this paper, reducing the high percentage of NTL (about 40%) in the Lebanese electric power utility, Electricité du Liban (EDL),[17] is accomplished by utilizing the latest state-of-the-art technology through the implementation of a PLC based AMI system.

OVERVIEW OF THE AMI SYSTEM

In 2012, the European Parliament, in the 2012/27/EC directive,[15] defined a Smart Metering or intelligent metering system as “an electronic system that can measure energy consumption, providing more information than a conventional meter, and can transmit and receive data using a form of electronic communication. Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications can be deployed in devices with capabilities to communicate without the need of human intervention.

The captured event-driven data is sent through the communication channel (wired or wireless) to the servers in charge of extracting and processing the data and generating responses (Jaewoo *et al.*, 2014).[23] Integration of smart meters into electricity grid involves implementation of a variety of

techniques and software, and the design of a smart meter depends on the requirements of the power utility as well as the customer (Depuru *et al.*, 2011).[13]

Besides the control and management capabilities provided by the implementation of the smart metering, the obtained metering data together with additional information can be used for other applications, such as predictive and load management systems.

Smart meters' capabilities of real-time voltage measurement and communication between the consumers and network controllers are potential key players in voltage control (Gao e Redfern, 2011).[18]

The ability of smart meters for bidirectional communication of data enables the ability to collect information regarding the electricity fed back to the power grid from customer premises.

Smart metering systems are necessary in billing applications. The SMs get the tariff costs in real time, in advance or through pre-programmed tariffs and then the cost of the supplied energy is calculated. The most common billing techniques are pricing depending on the time of use, realtime pricing, and peak consumption-dependent pricing (Murat *et al.*, 2014).[32] Smart meters can limit the maximum electricity consumption, and can terminate or re-connect electricity supply to any customer remotely (Vojdani, 2008).[41]

Architecture of an AMI System An AMI system implies the deployment of a heterogeneous infrastructure, including metering devices, communication networks, and data gathering and processing systems, as well as the associated management and installation duties. Such a system is based on four main pillars:

- A Smart Metering device, SM,
- A data gathering device, Data Concentrator (DC),
- A communication system used for data flow,
- A centralized management and control system, Control Center (CC).

The built-in two-way communication structure between smart energy meter and Head End System (HES) is capable of providing remote reading, monitoring & control of meters (consumer, feeder, distribution transformers meters etc.).

Data concentrator

A data concentrator is the core of data and energy management in an AMI. It provides the technology to measure and collect energy usage data. The concentrator can also be programmed to analyze and communicate this information to the central utility database. Not only can the utility providers could use this information for billing services, but can improve customer relationships through enhanced consumer services such as real-time energy analysis and communication of usage information. Additional benefits of fault detection and initial diagnosis can also be

achieved, further optimizing the operational cost. DCs are usually located inside Medium Voltage/Low Voltage (MV/LV) substations, and may include additional features such as LV supervision.

Communication system

Communication technologies play a key role, as they have to be cost-efficient and should provide good coverage, security features, bandwidth, and power quality with the least possible number of repetitions (Depuru *et al.*, 2011).[13] Communications in power grids have evolved from one-way communication systems and radial topology to bidirectional systems with network topology.

Control centre

The Control Center is in charge of receiving and storing the metering data for further processing. The CC can be seen as a modular system formed by the Meter Data Management System (MDMS), which manages the metering data, and additional secondary modules in charge of end-users' applications. Such applications constitute, among others, forecasting systems, geographical information systems, control applications, and load management. The MDMS includes tools that enable communication among different modules, as well as being in charge of validating, processing, and editing the metering data for a suitable information interchange among the different parts of the Smart Metering system (Mohassel *et al.*, 2014).[31] Making the most of information from SMs and Smart Grids (SGs) increasingly

requires dealing with Big Data. Diamantoulakis *et al.*[14] present a roadmap of Big Data analytics in Demand Energy Management that includes, among other strategies, load patterns categorization, predictive analytics, distributed data mining, and cloud computing, to assess different aspects of the SGs that cannot be solved with conventional data processing techniques

(Diamantoulakis *et al.*, 2015).[14]

GLOBAL TRENDS IN AMI COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

Technology adoption for AMI implementation globally varies by region. In North America and Europe, PLC and Radio Frequency (RF) mesh are most often deployed, with a greater tendency toward PLC technology in Europe than in the U.S. This is largely because grids in Europe connect an average number of electricity consumers per one transformer of about 76 compared to 15 in the U.S. For example, Italy and Sweden - two leaders in AMI deployment - employ PLC technology as the most economical solution in areas with a high population density, whereas the opposite tends to be true in North America and Japan where the average number of electricity consumers per one transformer is about 15.

Often, technology choices are driven by local regulations. Many countries, Germany among them, restrict use of RF mesh technologies, as unlicensed frequencies have raised concerns about interference.

Cellular communications technology is in limited deployment in private utility networks around the world and is more commonly used for commercial metering or data backhaul applications in North America. However, this technology has found broader applications for residential metering in countries such as Australia.

The Lebanese electric power utility (EDL) falls into the category of PLC technology for its AMI deployment since it connects an average of 55 customers per one transformer as the case in Europe for highdensity residential area (based on 1.2 million meters and about 22000 MV/LV transformers) among other supporting reasons, which will be outlined below.

The Lebanese AMI System

The inefficient and insufficiently guarded electrical grid has left EDL susceptible to security threats; inhibited alternative energy/conservations goals; and contributed to reliability problems, such as power quality disturbances and blackouts. Smart Grid is regarded by experts and decision makers as the solution to EDL's conventional electrical system.[40] To remedy the situation a large number of sensors are deployed to monitor a variety of critical functions and, consequently, report the information to both EDL and the consumer, thus allowing the latter to better understand his consumption patterns.

The AMI system, will allow to accurately identify network losses, detect tamper,

fraud, and network outages, manage NTL, improve revenue recovery, balance power flow and financial transaction processing, allow the possibility to make multi-tariff structures, provide pre-paid billing functionalities, peak load shaving measures and load management functionalities, and finally increase operational efficiency and lower operational expenses (Chaaban *et al.*, 2015).[3,8]

The Lebanese AMI system shall be composed of a Meter Data Management (MDM), Billing, and Customer Relationship Management (CRM), and an "AMI-MDM & Billing/CRM" Monitoring Center. In parallel to the ongoing implementation of the AMI system, another ongoing project - the "Distribution Service Provider" (DSP) (MoEW, 2010)[29], aims at outsourcing the complete distribution network services, including planning, design, expansion, operation and maintenance, metering, and bill collection. The AMI system project covers the implementation and replacement of all conventional metering of Lebanon by automatic meters controlled remotely through a central AMI system.

In summary, the Lebanese AMI system includes a Metering Control Center hosting the AMI software packages (Meter Reading and MDM) installed and run by EDL at its headquarter and smart meters installed at all levels by the DSPs in their respective regions. The installation of smart meters at the M1 (generation bus bar), M2 (HV/MV

substation) and M3 (MV outgoing feeder) levels has already been completed. Installations of smart meters at the M4 (private and public MV/LV substations) and M5 (customer) levels are under way.

Communications Solution

The successful implementation of any AMI system relies heavily on the choice of the communication technology. Different aspects such as the final application, the features of the location, and the topology electricity grid, among others, influence the choice of the most suitable technology. There is a wide range of available technologies for the communication network of an AMI system; however, there is currently no communications technology that fits all needs and sometimes more than one technology is used in the same deployment (Chaaban *et al.*, 2015 and Lipošcak e Boškovic, 2013). [3,8, 27]

Two main groups can be distinguished in Smart Metering technologies: wireless and wired. Wireless technologies usually entail less deployment costs and quicker installation, and they are more suitable for remote or hardly accessible locations (Parikh *et al.*, 2010).[36] Wired alternatives, on the other hand, do not present interference problems from other sensors of the network that may occur in wireless technologies.

When it comes to determining the right technology mix for the communications components, there may not be a one-size-fits-all solution or single technology that can meet all the needs of SG

networks. Electric power utilities implementing AMI systems shall take into consideration the following:

- Its unique circumstances, including the existing communications infrastructure available to support connectivity to the smart grid network;
- Service area terrain, population density, local regulations, and future SG applications;
- Latest state-of-the-art technologies, architectures, functionalities;
- Latest international seminars and conferences related to European and Regional SG and Metering; and
- Other utilities implementing AMI systems.

While choosing the right communications solution for a utility is critical, in many cases, a multi-technology approach will provide the best route for realizing the most value from its SG deployment.

In addition to providing solutions that can integrate and support multiple technologies on a single platform, utilities, migrating to the new technologies, must meet specific technology and customer requirements every step of the way.

OVERVIEW OF THE LEBANESE ELECTRIC POWER SECTOR

Electricité du Liban is the national electric power utility of Lebanon providing the generation, transmission These high losses resulting from NTL have jeopardized the sustainability of the power sector in Lebanon. Although

and distribution needs of the entire country. EDL,[17] an autonomous state-owned power utility owns roughly 90% of the installed generation capacity, in addition to the transmission and distribution networks (MoEW, 2010, Akkawi and Jaber, 2005).[2,4,29]

The power grid of EDL consists of several high voltage networks (66 kV, 150 kV, and 220 kV) in addition to the interconnection with networks in eight neighboring countries, namely Egypt, Jordan, Syria, and Turkey, through the 400kV transmission lines, and a 400/220 kV substation.

The technical and non-technical losses along the transmission and distribution networks are not uniform as they vary between provinces from around 9.6% up to 58% and then between regions from 15% up to 78% (MoEW, 2010 and EDL 2009). [29,30] Non-collected bills constitute a substantial component of these NTL.

The current status for meter reading is still carried out manually, and this method is subject to human error that could result in false data consequently incorrect bills (Ghajar e Khalife, 2003).[19] The NTL which represent the main cause of the losses are estimated to be 28% of the total losses of which 6% consists of the uncollectible (CRA International, 2006).[11] EDL's yearly average losses are presented in Table 1.

efforts for minimizing TL have been initiated (Akkawi e Chaaban,

2016),[3,8] more efforts are still needed.

EDL's AMI Communication Architecture

Table 2 presents a capital cost comparison between the two main options for communications, PLC and

- For very remote locations where a PLC based concentrator cannot be justified, the solution will be to communicate directly to the meter from the AMI Centre. To facilitate this, the meter will have to be connected to a GPRS modem

Table 2: Capital Cost Comparison.

Capital Cost Comparison	PLC	RF Mesh
Number of Smart Meters	1,200,000	1,200,000
Number of Meters with modems	1,000,000	1,000,000
Number of concentrators	18,000	1,200
Cost of Meter Modems (USD)	5	80
Cost of Concentrator Modems (USD)	5	80
Total Costs (USD)	5,090,000	80,096,000

RF Mesh.

A PLC based communication technology for EDL's AMI project is regarded as the most appropriate option for solving EDL's high NTL. Accordingly, service providers shall deploy about 18,000 PLC based DCUs, about 1.2 million PLC based smart meters, and other interface devices. The DCUs will communicate with the smart meters which are connected to the 18,000 public MV/LV substations using Narrowband PLC technology. Private MV/LV substations (about 4000) will be communicated directly with the CC through GPRS communication.

PLC communication modules will be installed in both the 1.2 million SMs and the 18,000 concentrators. The concentrators will gather data from the meters throughout the day and store this in the concentrator for collection by the Central AMI system.

Alternative communications configurations to PLC which may be implemented by service providers:

- instead of the PLC modem.
- Where there are a number of meters together such as in a meter room for an apartment block, meters may be connected through RS485 connections to master meters which then connect over PLC to the concentrators.
- For some areas where customer density is low, for example in rural areas, switch to GPRS communication technologies.

The Master Station at the Central AMI system will manage the communications from the center to the systems provided by the Service Providers. All communications from the Head End system will be over GPRS, mobile data communications.

There will be two types of communications from the center; regular scheduled communications from the Head End system to collect data from the concentrators (or the alternative configurations). This will

typically be an overnight task to collect the previous day's data. The other type is the urgent communications such as checking a meter reading, reconnection, etc., where a task to send a particular message to a particular meter or group of meters is launched.

Accordingly, the most suitable architecture for communication is summarized as:

- Narrowband PLC communication between the meters and concentrators. In this case there will be a PLC modem in each meter and each concentrator.
- Meters connected together by RS485 connectors for buildings such as apartment blocks. In this case there will only be PLC modems in the master meter (often two for resilience).
- Some meters with GPRS modems for remote locations where the cost of a concentrator is not justified. This is usually a very small percentage of the total meters.

SOLUTION TO EDL'S HIGH POWER SYSTEM LOSSES

Encountered electricity theft techniques in the country include direct connection to the power grid, using alternate neutral lines, meter tampering, in addition to other means such as tapping off a nearby paying consumer, and using magnets to slow down the spinning discs in the traditional electromechanical meter housing.

Utilizing an AMI system will, accurately, determine NTL when the smart meters' input and output are read

simultaneously (Greentech Media Inc., 2012).[20] AMI data could be effectively used for reduction of NTL especially electricity theft. This could be implemented by two methods: big data analysis and event management system that remotely report any tamper in smart meters. For the first case a method for identifying electrical theft by AMI data is presented (Mashima, 2012).[28] In these methods, the collected meter data are used for identifying possible electricity theft situations and abnormal consumption trends (Jokar *et al.*, 2016).[24] Smart Metering deployments are considered the first step in the path towards the SG (Oksa *et al.*, 2006).[35] By 2015, an estimated total of 65 million smart meters have been installed in the U.S. (U.S. Department of Energy, 2014) and this number keeps increasing. As more smart meters with communications are deployed, concerns regarding data security and integrity arise (Ye *et al.*, 2015).

Smart Metering must not be regarded just as a mere data gathering application, but a two way communication system that allows remote operations (e.g.: connection and disconnection), which are critical for advanced operation of the grid and its evolution. Reusing existing infrastructure makes PLC the natural technology to connect meters to the central premises of the utility.

Utilities are evaluating the use of Narrowband PLC (NB-PLC) in Smart Metering deployments. These technologies have been selected in

several European countries after undergoing detailed technical and economical evaluations (Sendin *et al.*, 2015).[38] NB-PLC technologies have proven themselves a cost-effective solution when the distribution network has certain specific topologies. Smart Metering networks are being deployed all over the world and NBPLC technologies are a successful choice for certain network topologies.

Most of the NB-PLC systems available in the market are extending the frequency bands in order to improve the performance of the communications. This initiative is aimed to increase the performance and facilitate the introduction of these solutions to new regions.

The market is permanently working to provide cost effective solutions for utilities that need to deploy smart meters in important volumes, normally in the order of millions. Several NB-PLC technologies are offering implementations using frequency bands from 40 kHz to 500 kHz, covering CENELEC, ARIB and FCC bands.

Local authorities in the Middle East require enough bandwidth in the LV section of the distribution grid for new services such as LV distribution automation, real-time remote metering operations or the integration of distributed energy resources (DER) to be deployed. On the other hand, the deployments of NBPLC technologies in Europe have allowed the detection of some disturbances in low frequency bands that can be avoided by moving to

higher frequencies. The problems produced by interferences on PLC devices are being widely addressed by the research community.

NB-PLC technologies are regulated according to the essential requirements of the 2014/30/EU Directive in Europe, FCC part 15 in the US and ARIB in Japan. The main PLC technologies have been developed, or are developing, their specifications to cover the transmissions in the frequency bands from 40 kHz to 500 kHz. Due to the changes in the regulation and in order to adapt to new markets, PRIME released version 1.4 (PRIME Alliance, 2013)[37] of the protocol, to cover the complete frequency band from 42 kHz up to 471 kHz.

The Lebanese AMI project will allow, among other functions, to accurately identify network losses, detect tamper, fraud, and network outages, manage nontechnical losses, improve revenue recovery, balance power flow and financial transaction processing, allow the possibility to make multi-tariff structures, provide pre-paid billing functionalities, peak load shaving measures and load management functionalities, as well as increase operational efficiency and lower operational expenses and increase. The mechanism utilized in this project to reduce system losses is by correlating energy from generation to transmission, distribution, and customer levels.

The key functions within the MDM are the validation, cleansing and

estimation of missing data before it is analyzed or passed on for use. One of the key uses of this data for EDL is the identification of the losses between concentrators and meter consumption. Network losses including:

- Reconciliation of consumptions between concentrators and meter totals
- Totals and blocks during the day
- Trends over time for each concentrator

The Lebanese Energy Roadmap

Electricity losses in transmission and distribution systems in Lebanon is severe. Despite several efforts from the Lebanese government over the past decade to improve the performance of the power sector, the level of electricity losses has remained considerable. In this context, it was reported in the Standard & Poor's rating report released on March 1, 2019:

“we could revise the outlook to stable if the Lebanese government is able to advance substantial economic and fiscal reforms that would boost economic growth and reduce government debts levels over the medium term, including addressing the gaps and inefficiencies in the electricity sector.” Despite the drastic economic consequences of electricity losses, there is currently no systematic monitoring of electricity losses in Lebanon that allows determining its sources.

Figure 1 shows a simplified power system flowchart that represents the electricity transmission losses due to technical factors and geographic conditions. In contrast, once power

enters the distribution system, losses are both TL and NTL.

At present, electricity is metered at the following levels in the energy roadmap:

1. M1: Electronic meters installed on the generation bus bars feeding into the transmission network. Status: existing.
2. M2: Electronic meters installed on the secondary side of the main HV/MV substations. Status: existing.
3. M3: Smart meters installed at the beginning of each MV feeder and were rolled out by the end of 2014 and installed since then on new MV feeders.
4. M4: Smart meters installed inside private and public MV/LV substations. Status: for private substations, installations are expected to be completed by the end of 2019; as for the public substations, installations are underway and expected to be completed by the end of 2021.
5. M5: Smart meters installed for endconsumers connected to the LV distribution network. Status: installations are underway and expected to be completed by the end of 2021.

Figure 1: Energy Roadmap

Availability of the Data

Across the utility industry, there is no uniformly defined approach for the calculation of losses because each utility power system is different and the availability of information and data varies from one utility to another.

Different reliable methodologies have been developed over the years to calculate losses based on the information available to each utility.

Separation of losses into technical and non-technical categories is one ultimate method for the assessment of electricity losses within each level in the power system chain. Using this analytical method of separation would help identify the likely causes of losses and their different types. However, NTL are more difficult to measure because they are often unaccounted for by the utility and thus have no recorded data.

In EDL, the availability of reliable information is a main challenge. The introduction of the smart meters at the distribution MV feeders in 2014, provided the utility with a consistent and accurate source of data. On the other hand, the current status of the M5 type meters' readings is done manually

For the distribution system, 6 regions were classified according to their geographic extent. The ratios are calculated i) for each calendar year and ii) as two-year totals.

Distribution system losses vary dramatically between the selected regions - lowest in the range (11 to 13 percent) and highest reaches the range (65 to 67 percent). That is, in relative terms, a significantly very high ratio of

mostly on a frequency of 2-month billing cycle. Several problems and shortcomings are typically encountered in such method. First, lining up the time periods for the energy distributed and sales is a challenge due to meter readings taking place across multiple billing cycles that do not necessarily correspond with the same time period that distributed energy represents. Second, due to readings obtained from manual-reading of the meter, error is introduced to loss calculation that could result from false data (Ghajar e Khalife, 2003).[19]

To mitigate these issues to some degree, it was essential to develop aggregate datasets on annual basis. This will allow for the determination of total system energy losses over a given year, and will provide a good indicator of overall system efficiency and lost revenue. The losses are calculated the follows:

34.0%

Comparison, Discussion, and Conclusion

Roughly 34 percent of the total electricity produced in Lebanon is lost in transmission and distribution (total for the 2015-2016 period) see Figure 2.

electricity lost that should be addressed, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Distribution Losses - by Region (2016).

There has been minimal variation in total electricity losses over the years 2015 and 2016. It is evident that losses, mostly NTL, are mainly concentrated in distribution, which account for almost 83 percent of the total losses.

These figures clearly suggest that measures to reduce electricity losses would have important economic returns on Lebanese economy in general and on EDL's financial standing. Indeed, it is widely

considered that reforming the electricity sector is a key transit to reversing the outlook on the Lebanese economy due to its staggering weight on the fiscal budget and economic growth, as assessed by Standard & Poor's in its rating report. The Lebanese Ministry of Energy & Water's updated Policy paper for the Electricity Sector (MoEW, 2019) presented in Table 3 the projected values for the TL & NTL for the period 2018-2025.

Table 3: Schedule to Reduce the Rates of TL and NTL (MoEW, 2019).[30]

Type of Losses	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
TL (Transmission)	4	3.5	3.5	3.5	3	3	3	3
TL (Distribution)	13	9.8	7.2	6	5	5	5	5
NTL (Distribution)	21	14	7	3	3	3	3	3
Total Losses	38	27.3	17.7	12.5	11	11	11	11

Although the complete rollout of the Lebanese AMI project will be completed by end of 2021, but the mechanism utilized in this project to reduce system losses, by correlating energy from generation to

transmission, distribution, and customer levels; has reduced the distribution system losses for the first half of 2019 from 33.8% to 28%, as detailed in Table 4 and Figure 4 below.

Table 4: Distribution System Losses for the First Half of 2019.

	Distributed Energy (GWh)	Billed Consumed Energy (GWh)			Total Distribution Losses (%)
		MV/LV Customers	Public Sector & Refugees Camps	Total (GWh)	
Beirut	1,041	754	224	978	6
Bekaa	463	138	50	188	59
North Lebanon	563	224	17	241	57
Northern Mount Lebanon	1,387	1,165	44	1,208	13
South Lebanon	935	314	236	549	41
South Mount Lebanon	1,639	1,093	59	1,152	30
Total	6,026	3,687	629	4,316	28

It is important to note that for the same period (first half of 2019) there are known losses due to unbilled consumed energy by the Syrian refugees camps, which are estimated to be 333 GWh. If this value is excluded from the above calculation would have reduced further the total distribution system losses from 28% to 22.8% (note that the target rate for the distribution system losses for 2019 is 23.8%, as per Table 3).

On April 6, 2019 France hosted in Paris the international conference in support of

Lebanon development and reforms, CEDRE ("Conférence économique pour

le développement, par les réformes et avec les entreprises"). Within the framework of the CEDRE conference, the Lebanese government has committed itself to undertake fundamental reforms in the sector (MoEW, 2019),[30] including:

1. Power Generation: Increase power generation using both thermal power plants and renewable energy.
2. Transmission: improve the network infrastructure to secure the vital requirements for the efficient and successful operation of distribution.
3. Distribution: new projects are required not only to expand the networks, but more importantly in the short term to reduce the

excessive losses. This would also contribute to reducing budget transfers to EDL.

4. Tariff: Adjust electricity tariffs to reduce EDL's losses.
5. As such, investing in SMs and a SG to control collection, ensure a better management of demand and supply and support EDL to limit its technical and non-technical losses.

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